

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16891316

Digital Cyberspace Cost And Performance Of Deposit Money Bank In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the digital cyberspace cost on firm performance of deposit money bank using data for the period of 2012-2023. The objectives of this study were to: determine the extent to which cyber security maintenance cost affects on firm performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria; evaluate the extent to which cyber security acquisition cost affects on firm performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria. Panel least squared (PLS) method of data analysis was adopted because of its Best Linear Unbiased Estimators (BLUE) properties. The data for the variables used was sourced from annual report of the selected deposit money bank in Nigeria. The variables were on cyber security maintenance cost and cyber security acquisition cost. The study adopted the descriptive statistics, correlation approach, as well as panel least square. E- View software was used for the analysis. The study found that Cyber security maintenance cost has significant effect on performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria. (t-test 3.491757, p=0.0008). Cyber security acquisition cost has no significant effect on performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria. (t-test 0.959399, p=0.3405). The study recommends that, Regular maintenance and updates of cybersecurity systems can improve performance by reducing downtime and protecting against emerging threats. Consider purchasing bundled cybersecurity solutions that include multiple features, such as antivirus, firewall, and intrusion detection, for a lower overall cost

Keywords: digital, cyberspace cost, firm performance, maintenance cost, cyber security acquisition

1. BINTRODUCTION

Cyberspace cost is a measure against cybercrime is the practice of protecting computers, networks, system servers, digital mobile devices, automated and electronic systems, and data from malicious, unauthorized, and unwarranted access and attacks. It is also regarded as information technology security or electronic information security used to protect data from unwanted cybercriminals (Mugari, et al., 2016). It is a fact today that a buoyant economy thrives on an effective, efficient, and secured financial system. Cyberspace costs are typically sloped toward deriving financial gains. Insurance firms, banks and other financial institutions, corporate businesses, and individuals bear the losses of such illicit acts. Insurance is a critical stakeholder in the financial sector that always has the activities of cybercriminals to contend with to stay afloat in this competitive business environment.

Cyberspace is a difficult environment that is always changing and evolving. As a result, personnel in charge of security in diverse sectors face problems in keeping up with advances in the cyber realm. A stable, safe, and resilient cyberspace is critical for economic growth and sustainability, especially in the banking sector (Khalil, Usman & Manzoor, 2020). As a result, insurance companies in Nigeria have continuously invested in cyber security to protect their database, prevent monetary losses, productivity losses, maintain company image, and remain afloat in the competitive business environment. However, despite this huge investment made by Nigeria banking firms, cyber hackers still attack, penetrate and have undue access to their cyber-space causing damages to both the institution and customers of the insurance industry. It is on this backdrop that this study set to investigate the effect of cyber security on the business sustainability of insurance firms in Nigeria.

The issue of cyberspace security remains a significant challenge in Nigeria and is evolving in both complexity and variety. The advancements and progress in technology that aim to move society towards a digital era also raise the vulnerability to cybercrime. Nigeria is rated among the countries showing the highest rates of cybercrimes globally (Dlamini and Mbambo, 2019). Cyberspace security is of utmost importance due to the sophisticated cyber attacks occurring, mainly in the banking sector. Cyberspace security is considered a vital industry to protect and secure both the bank and the customer (Al-Alawi et al., 2023; Stanikzai and Shah, 2021).

Cyberspace security is of critical importance, and the market labour of this sector has been undergoing numerous changes over the years. Cyber security is needed in the dynamic digitized banking sector (Al-Alawi et al., 2023). Despite persistent advantages, the concept of cyber security threats plays a significant role in the adoption and retention of the technology (Kimani et al., 2019; Tyagi, 2019). Therefore, the growing knowledge of the cyber threats is regarded as a driver that could potentially moderate the perception of customers towards the acceptance and retention of new technology (Jibril et al., 2020).

Cyberspace cost problems arise from the escalating sophistication and frequency of cyber attacks, resulting in financial losses, operational disruptions, and reputational damage for organizations. Implementing and maintaining cyber security technologies (firewalls, intrusion detection systems, etc.). Addressing cyber security incidents and data breaches (investigations, legal fees, notification to affected parties). Paying for cyber security insurance premiums. Lost business and revenue due to downtime, compromised systems, or reputational damage. Increased costs of operating due to increased security measures. Higher regulatory fines and penalties for data breaches.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to evaluate the digital cyberspace cost and firm performance of deposit money bank. This study specifically identified the following objectives:

- i. To determine the extent to which cyber security maintenance cost affects on firm performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria.
- ii. To evaluate the extent to which cyber security acquisition cost affects on firm performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses are formulated

Ho₁: Cyber security maintenance cost has no significant effect on performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria.

Ho₂: Cyber security acquisition cost has no significant effect on performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Cyberspace Cost

According to Akintoye et al. (2022) cyberspace cost refers to a series of practices and activities fashioned with a view to ensuring the protection of personal and organisational data, information and networks from all possible threats whether internally or externally induced. In terms of digital banking, Austin-Olowo et al. (2023) noted that cyberspace cost is the concept of safeguarding the digital banking services and

online transactions from adversity and hazards, such as information disclosure, theft or disruption of services it provides. In Nigeria, Cyberspace cost refers to measures that are employed by the banks and other enforcement authorities to safeguard and prevent incidents of cybercrimes (Chitimira and Ncube, 2021).

The practice of safeguarding systems, networks, applications, and databases from online threats is known as Cyberspace cost (Craig, Diakun-Thibault, & Purse, 2014). In the financial industry, Cyberspace cost means protecting sensitive financial data and important systems from online threats (Hasham, Joshi, & Mikkelsen, 2019). Cyberspace cost refers to a data framework utilized in opposing dangers from the internet, which may bargain the accessibility, honesty, or privacy of information (Njeru & Gaitho, 2019). Digital protection (Cyber security) is frequently utilized as a similar term for data security. Cyberspace cost is not really just the insurance of the actual internet, yet additionally the security of the individuals who work in the internet and any of their resources that can be reached by means of the internet (Albrechtsen & Hovden, 2010).

Firm Performance.

Aniitha (2018) defined the firm performance measure as the measure of how an organization can use its assets from its fundamental mode of business and generate revenues. Sound firm performance is critical for developing and maintaining a business in the current financial atmosphere. In any organization, firm performance can be measured through financial ratios. Organizational profitability dictates the extent to which the organization generates profit as a ratio to the value or degree of its profits (Muraguli et al., 2017). Ratio analysis as a measure of financial performance helps to identify firms' weaknesses and strengths by detecting anomalies in the financial statement and focusing attention on mutually important issues. The profitability of fruit processing firms is affected by either endogenous factors or exogenous structural factors that include the rate of technological advancement, policy decisions, expanding population workforce, and risks (Kariithi, 2017).

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Silber's Constraint Theory of Innovation which was postulated by Silber in 1975 in an attempt to provide rational motives for financial innovation employed by financial firms. The theory argues that financial innovation enhances the profitability of firms by reducing costs and increasing the speed at which financial services are delivered. The theory views that banks have both internal and external constraints which can be managed through the adoption of technologically enabled processes and products. Furthermore, the theory recognizes regulation as one of the key constraints to be overcome (Weill & Woerner, 2013). Scholars such as Tufano (2003), Gakure and Ngumi (2013) have supported the validity of the theory on the grounds of its applicability in predicting financial performance and establishing a competitive advantage in the marketplace. The theory has however been criticized as either being unconfirmed empirically or excessively focused on financial innovation to the detriment of other factors.

Notwithstanding the aforementioned criticisms, this theory is considered relevant for this study for a number of reasons. First, it recognizes the centrality of regulation as one of the motivations for financial innovation and we posit that cyber security measures proposed in this study as a panacea to the challenge of financial innovation will only work under an atmosphere of compliance to a robust risk management framework facilitated by regulation (Harris, 2016).

Second, the theory is in alignment with the profit maximization objective of financial services sector where deposit money banks feature prominently. Additionally, in delivering financial innovation, the theory distinguishes technology as either physical (computers and networks related) or miscellaneous (applied information) and these two complements are fully at play when considering cyber security architecture for deposit money banks

Empirical Review

Natile and Sheila (2025) identified cyber security threats that hinder the adoption of digital banking and provide sustainable strategies to combat cyber security risks in the banking industry. Systematic literature review guidelines were used to conduct a quantitative synthesis of empirical evidence regarding the impact of cyber security threats and risks on the adoption of digital banking. A total of 84 studies were initially examined, and after applying the selection and eligibility criteria for this systematic review, 58 studies were included. These selected articles consistently identified identity theft, malware attacks, phishing and vishing as significant cyber security threats that hinder the adoption of digital banking.

Asta and Rasheed, (2024) investigated the security impact of cyber security management on the digital economy across sub-Saharan African countries using Nigeria and Cameroon as a case study. To achieve these goals, the study considered three specific objectives such as examining the past and current trend of cyber-crimes perpetrated in the digital economy of the selected sub-Saharan African countries, examining the nature and types of cyber security protocols and already established laws in combating cyber-crimes in the digital economy; and also evaluating the roles of economy stakeholders in the repositioning and enforcement of cyber security protocols in effectively combating cyber-crimes in the digital economy. This study adopted a descriptive design. The research is constructed using a mixed research strategy (quantitative and qualitative methods; primary and secondary data collection and analysis) to highlight the main findings (three hypothesized research questions are tested about respondents' views using content analysis of semi-structured interviews and triangulation of the results) and draw a valid and reliable conclusion.

Imoh, Emengini and Imoh, (2023) investigated the degree of influence cyber security efficacy exerts on financial performance using primary source for data collection. Fintech companies in Nigeria were taken as the study population. Cyber security efficacy was operationalized in terms of access restriction capacity (ARC), attack resistance capacity (ATC) and self-preservation capacity (SPC), while return on asset (ROA) was used as proxies of financial performance. Top management support was utilized as the contextual factor in relating cyber security efficacy to financial performance. Multiple linear regression technique was used as the principal tool of statistical analysis while Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was used in supporting role. On the final analysis, it was found that analysis produced evidence that access restrictions capacity of digital products of Fintech companies in Nigeria significantly exerts positive influence on their return on assets. Also, analysis showed that attack resistance capacity of digital products of Fintech companies in Nigeria exerts significant positive influence on their return on assets. It was also found that self-preservation capacity of digital products of Fintech companies in Nigeria exerts significant positive influence on their return on assets.

Khalid, et al. (2021) conducted a meta-analytical review to analyze the association among cyber security costs, such as prevention and detection costs (PDC), response costs (RC), development costs (DC), and indirect costs (IC), on the e-banking product innovation performance (PIP) and financial performance (FP), b) to evaluate the causal association of cyber security costs, i.e., (PDC, RC, DC, and IC) on PIP and FP; and c) investigate the mediating effects of PIP in a relationship between PDC, RC, DC, IC and FP. The study sample was the managerial cadre employees of various electronic banks (e-banks) working in Pakistan. The survey was conducted by distributing the questionnaire among the employees of e-banks working in Pakistan. The collected data were estimated via multivariate statistical techniques. The results of the study showed that a) the costs associated with cyber security, specifically PDC, RC, and DC, have a statistically significant effect on PIP and e-banking FP, whereas IC has a negative significant influence on the PIP and FP, b) the PIP has a statistically significant effect on e-banking FP, and c) the PIP partially mediates an association between PDC, RC, DC, and FP, whereas, PIP insignificantly mediates in a relationship amongst IC and e-banking FP. The study will be applicable in the modern electronic banking (e-banking) systematic risk control and information security solution.

Akintoye, et al. (2022) examined the impact of cyber security in driving the financial innovation of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. The rapid growth in population coupled with the challenge of reducing the rate of the financially excluded has made the need for financial innovation by Deposit Money Banks

in Nigeria a matter of serious importance. However, due to a mix of factors ranging from poor design, design vulnerabilities to lopsided adoption and implementation of new financial technology products, this need has remained largely unmet with attendant negative consequences on the financial system. The study adopted a survey research design with primary data obtained via a structured questionnaire administered to a sample size of fifty-six (56) Deposit Money Banks Staff purposively selected. The sampled staffs were senior member staff of key impacted departments while the Banks selected accounted for 93% of total market capitalization as on December 31, 2021. The primary data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study found that cyber security proxied by risk management and bank monitoring had a statistically and positively significant impact on financial innovation of deposit money banks in Nigeria (Adj.R2= 0.447, F (2,55) =23.274, p< 0.05).

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Ex-Post Fact research design was employed for this study. An *Ex-post Facto* research determines the cause-effect relationship among variables. *Ex-post Facto* seeks to find out the factors that are associated with certain occurrence, conditions, events or behaviours by analyzing past events or already existing data for possible casual factors (Kothari & Garg 2014).

Nature and Source of Data Collection

Data were collected from only secondary sources. The data were extracted from audited annual accounts of the banks. The data to be extracted include; cyber security maintenance cost (CSMC) and cyber security acquisition cost (CSQC) as the independent variables while return on assets (ROA) is the dependent variable.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consists of the fourteen (14) deposit money banks quoted on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX). The study will cover twelve years annual reports and accounts of these banks from 2012 to 2013.

Determination of Sample Size

This study selected all the ten (10) deposit money banks in Nigeria for the study. The banks were chosen because of proximity of data

List of Quoted Deposit Money Banks on the Nigerian Exchange Group

1	Fidelity bank plc
2	FCMB plc
3	First bank plc
4	Access bank plc
5	United bank of Africa (UBA)
6	Eco bank plc
7	Sterling bank plc

Model Specification

In an attempt to determine the tax mix on capital investment, we develop an empirical model to ascertain the association that exists between the variables. Specification of economic model is based on accounting theory and from prior empirical work on the variables. The multiple regression model used was adapted from the work of Imoh, Emengini and Imoh, (2023) who investigated the degree of influence cyber security efficacy exerts on financial performance. Their model is: $ROA = F(ARC, ATC, SPC)$

Where:

ROA – Return on assets

ARC - Access restriction capacity

ATC - Attack resistance capacity

SPC - Self-preservation capacity

This model was adapted into:

$ROA = F(CSMC, CSAC)$

Where

ROA – Return on assets
 CSMC – Cyber Security Maintenance Cost
 CSAC - Cyber Security Acquisition Cost
 F = Functional Notation
 Our model can be restated in an econometric form as:
 $ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CSMC_{it} + \beta_2 CSAC_{it} + u_{it}$
 Where
 β_0 = Autonomous Intercept
 β_1 = Coefficient of parameter CSMC
 β_2 = Coefficient of parameter CSAC
 U = Stochastic error term

Method of Data Analysis

The data analysis used pre-test such as: descriptive statistics and inferential statistics using 95% confidence interval as in Aiken and West (1991).

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTEPRETATION

Result Interpretation

In order to examine the relationship between the dependent variable (Return on Assets) and the independent variables (CSMC, CSAC) and to test the formulated hypothesis, we employed a Panel Regression Analysis since the data had both time series (2012-2023) and longitudinal properties (7 quoted Banka) our analysis is presented in table 4.3 below

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LCSMC_{it} + \beta_2 LCSAC_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Summary of regression result

Dependent Variable: ROA
 Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section weights)
 Date: 03/23/25 Time: 11:41
 Sample: 2012 2023
 Periods included: 12
 Cross-sections included: 7
 Total panel (unbalanced) observations: 83
 Linear estimation after one-step weighting matrix

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.214767	0.252496	4.811028	0.0000
CSMC	0.063986	0.018325	3.491757	0.0008
CSAC	0.068552	0.071453	0.959399	0.3405

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)

Weighted Statistics

R-squared	0.659402	Mean dependent var	0.583728
Adjusted R-squared	0.645554	S.D. dependent var	0.389949
S.E. of regression	0.258618	Sum squared resid	4.949344
F-statistic	6.412099	Durbin-Watson stat	1.634417
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000003		

Unweighted Statistics

R-squared	0.565580	Mean dependent var	0.526145
Sum squared resid	5.033540	Durbin-Watson stat	1.675369

The results presented above will be analyzed using two criteria; Accounting a priori criteria, and statistical criteria

C. Accounting a priori Criteria

The a priori expectation is used to determine the existing Accounting theories and this indicates the signs and magnitude of our variables.

4. A regression line intercept of 0.214767 is displayed in the result in table 4.3. With a p-value of 0.0000, which is less than 0.05, the t-test result is 4.811028, which is positive and statistically significant. This suggests that when there is no change in the explanatory variables, the return on asset value will remain constant at 21.0% per cent annually.
5. Regression result demonstrates a statistically significant positive correlation between cyber security maintenance costs. cyber security maintenance costs has a value of 0.063986, which suggests that a 1% increase in cyber security maintenance costs will, ceteris paribus, result in a 6% improvement in business performance. This is in line with the apriori prediction. This finding bolsters the theory that raising cyber security maintenance costs will improve cyber space perceptions of firm performance and value.
6. There is a positive relationship between cyber security acquisition costs and firm performance. The cyber security acquisition costs value is 0.068552. This suggests that a one percent drop in the cyber security acquisition costs will, ceteris paribus, result in a rise in performance value of roughly forty-three percent. This is in line with the apriori prediction. This finding corroborates the theory that larger firms in Nigeria do better than smaller ones.

D. Statistical Criteria

The leverage showed positive and significant results, with a t-value of 3.491757 and a p-value of 0.0.0008, respectively. Their p-value was less than the 5% level of significance, which explains this. According to this finding, cyber security maintenance costs is favorable and has no bearing on the value that Nigerian deposit money banks have for their performance

In Nigeria, the value that cyber security acquisition costs on deposit money banks is positively correlated with the firm performance. Their t-value of 0.959399 and p-value of 0.3405, which was less than the five percent level of significance, respectively, demonstrated this. This finding indicates that variations in the cyber security acquisition costs of deposit money banks in Nigeria are significantly influenced by the size of the organization.

Based on the outcome, the coefficient of determination R² is 0.659402, meaning that the independent variables in the model— cyber security acquisition costs, cyber security maintenance costs —explain 65% of the variation in performance. Conversely, factors outside of our model account for roughly 35% of the total. This demonstrates even more how well the model fits the data.

The associated probability value of 0.000 indicates that the model's f-statistics value of 6.412099, which measures the combined importance of the explanatory variables, is judged to be statistically significant at the 1 percent level. This suggests that the dependent and independent variables differ significantly from one another.

Hypotheses Testing

The need to examine the relationship between the collected data and the stated hypothesis has called for this section. This result will be compared with the statistical criteria to see if the preconceived notion in this research work holds or not. However, if the probability value is less than 0.05%, alternative hypothesis is accepted, but when it is greater than 5% hull hypothesis is accepted

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Cyber security maintenance cost has no significant effect on performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria.

From the result report of our t-test in table 4.3 above, it was observed from Cyber security maintenance cost the value of 0.3.491757 with the probability of 0.0008 which is not within the desired level of

significant (0.05), we therefore reject alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypotheses and conclude that Cyber security maintenance cost has significant effect on performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂ Cyber security acquisition cost has no significant effect on performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria.

From the forgoing result we find out that computed value for firm age is 0.959399 while it's probability is 0.3405 this shown that the Cyber security acquisition cost is statistically insignificant. Based on this analysis we reject (H1) and accept (H0), which implies that Cyber security acquisition cost has no significant effect on performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

Cybersecurity costs can include expenses for technology, personnel, and training. The specific costs of cyber security can vary depending on the size and complexity of the organization. Cyber security costs can be direct, such as the cost of purchasing security software, or indirect, such as the cost of lost productivity due to cyber attacks. It's important to consider both the costs and benefits of cyber security when making investment decisions, as strong cyber security can protect against financial losses and reputational damage. In conclusion, cyber risk poses a significant threat to the financial system's stability, as evidenced by the economic consequences of cyber attacks on financial institutions in both the United States and Nigeria. These attacks result in financial losses for individual banks and undermine customer trust in the security of the overall financial system.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made as follows:

1. Regular maintenance and updates of cybersecurity systems can improve performance by reducing downtime and protecting against emerging threats..
2. Consider purchasing bundled cybersecurity solutions that include multiple features, such as antivirus, firewall, and intrusion detection, for a lower overall cost.

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